

Innovative drug delivery in ophthalmology

Kiril Genov¹

1 Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Sofia, Zdrave Str. 2, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Dunav Str. 2, Sofia 1000, Bulgaria

3 Department of Propedeutics of Internal Medicine, UMHAT Alexandrovska, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Sofia, Georgi Sofijski Str. 1, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Department of Ophthalmology, Eye Clinic, University Hospital Alexandrovska, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Krassimira Yoncheva (kyoncheva@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

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Abstract

Ocular drug delivery (topical or intraocular) is hindered by physiological barriers, including the mucus layer, surface epithelium, tear drainage, enzyme metabolism, and the blood–aqueous and blood–retina barriers. Conventional dosage forms face problems related to short retention time and poor drug bioavailability. The development of nanoparticles as drug delivery systems is an advantageous strategy that could overcome these limitations. Nanoparticles can prolong the retention time on the ocular surface, allowing more effective contact with the epithelium. In addition, they can reduce the side effects of drugs due to their capability to release the drug at a desired rate. Finally, nanoparticles can improve the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs, further enabling their absorption. The present review summarizes recent research on the development of three types of nanoparticles as carriers for ophthalmic drug delivery, particularly polymeric micelles, nanogels, and nanocrystals.

Keywords

Nanocrystals, nanogels, ocular drug delivery, polymeric micelles

Introduction

Eye diseases are one of the main challenges of our time, affecting millions of people around the world. Leading causes of visual impairment and blindness are various eye diseases such as cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, and diabetic retinopathy. Despite the progress of modern medicine, ophthalmological therapies often face insufficient effectiveness. One of the main reasons is related to inappropriate drug properties (e.g., poor solubility), drug metabolism by enzymes in ocular tissues, and drug binding to tear proteins. Furthermore, the complex anatomy of the eye and rapid elimination of the applied drugs lead to less than 5% of

the drug reaching the cornea. The turnover of lacrimal fluid (1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$) additionally lowers the concentration of the drug on the eye surface. The latter makes the treatment of the diseases of the anterior and posterior segments of the eye ineffective. Thus, different approaches have to be searched for, aiming to overcome these limitations. Such approaches include administration of dosage forms with optimal viscosity, pH, and tonicity. In particular, the development of highly viscous solutions, semisolid (gels, ointments), and solid dosage forms (inserts) ensures longer residence time of the instilled dose. Similarly, the adjustment of the pH and tonicity of the drug products to the physiological values of tear fluid overcomes excessive tear secretion and prolongs

the residence. Nevertheless, some of the problems of ocular therapies remain unresolved. In this view, there is a need for innovative dosage forms that would be able to improve drug penetration and bioavailability upon ocular administration.

One of the most attractive new strategies is the encapsulation of drugs into nanoparticles (Onugwu et al. 2023). The main advantages of the nanosized particles are related to their capacity to prolong the retention time, to provide sustained release of the loaded drug, and to improve cellular uptake (Diebold and Calonge 2010; Zhou et al. 2013; Li et al. 2023). In addition, the surface functionalization of nanoparticles with appropriate ligands could provide targeted delivery to anterior and posterior ocular segments. Furthermore, the toxicity or irritating effects of some of the drugs could be decreased by inclusion in nanoparticles. The nanoparticles could be prepared with different carriers (e.g., polymeric, metal, or inorganic), but the most preferred carriers are biopolymers. Among them, the polysaccharides (chitosan, sodium alginate, and hyaluronic acid) are intensively investigated. The main advantages of the mentioned polysaccharides are their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and low toxicity, as well as mucoadhesiveness (Kumar et al. 2016; Yoncheva 2020).

The aim of the present review is to summarize the recent research regarding the development of polymeric micelles, nanogels, and nanocrystals as carriers for ophthalmic drug delivery. These types of nanoparticles were selected because of their simple preparation under mild conditions.

Polymeric micelles

Micelles are self-assembling nanoparticles consisting of a core and a shell with a typical size in the range of 5–100 nm (Fig. 1). Typically, the micelles could be formulated from amphiphilic polymers or low-molecular surfactants. Among them, the polymeric micelles are the most important since they possess higher stability upon dilution because of their low critical micellar concentration (CMC). It is the low CMC that ensures high stability and prevents the disaggregation of the structure upon dilution in *in vivo* conditions. Thus, in the hydrophilic physiological medium, the hydrophobic chains are associated in the core, while the hydrophilic segments are externally orientated, forming the shell. Because of this specific core-shell structure, the micelles could load hydrophobic drugs in the core to a very high degree, which further improves their absorption (Yoncheva et al. 2012).

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of polymeric micelles, nanogels, and nanocrystals.

With the help of the micelles, drug delivery to the eye has been significantly improved in recent years. Some examples of various types of micelles as ocular drug delivery systems are presented in Table 1. Terbinafine was loaded in micelles prepared with the non-ionic surfactant macrogol 15 hydroxystearate for the topical treatment of fungal keratitis (Zhou et al. 2017). *In vivo* studies revealed that the micelles delivered considerably higher concentrations of the drug into rabbit corneas with or without de-epithelialization compared to the simple oily solution of the drug. Rapamycin was loaded in poly(ethylene glycol)-distearoyl phosphatidylethanolamine micelles for the topical treatment of autoimmune dacryoadenitis in a mouse model of Sjögren's syndrome (Shah et al. 2017). The study demonstrated the opportunity to avoid the use of irritating vehicles for this hydrophobic drug by its formulation in the core of the micelles. Similarly, the solubility of hydrophobic cyclosporine was improved via its encapsulation in micelles based on Ploxamer 407-D- α -tocopheryl polyethylene glycol 1000 succinate (Grimaudo et al. 2018).

As mentioned above, the increase in drug solubility is one of the main advantages of micelles that further enables improvement of drug bioavailability. Fexofenadine was loaded in mixed micelles based on Pluronic P123 and F127 intended for the treatment of allergic conjunctivitis (El-Shahed et al. 2024). The *in vivo* study revealed that the micellar drug restored the conjunctival mucosa with normal thickness and normal lamina propria, whereas the pure drug resulted in a partial improvement in rabbits. The authors concluded that the enhancement might be due to the improved drug solubility and mucoadhesiveness of the micelles. Resveratrol, a stilbenoid with antioxidant properties, was also loaded in Pluronic F127 or Pluronic F127/casein micelles, having in mind its capacity to scavenge reactive oxygen species responsible for long-term eye diseases (Vivero-Lopez et al. 2022). The micelles increased resveratrol solubility 50-fold and favored its permeability through corneal and scleral tissues. The authors concluded that the micellar formulation could effectively supply resveratrol to the anterior and posterior eye segments. Polymeric micelles based on Soluplus® (polyvinyl caprolactam-polyvinyl acetate-polyethylene glycol copolymer) were developed as a nanocarrier for α -lipoic acid (Alvarez-Rivera et al. 2016). The micelles enhanced more than 10-fold the solubility of α -lipoic acid and demonstrated *in situ* transformation into weak gels (which was expected to increase corneal residence time at 35 °C) and enhanced the drug accumulation in bovine cornea.

Thus, the increased drug solubility facilitates transcorneal permeation and improves bioavailability. Imatinib was loaded in polymeric micelles based on hyaluronic acid derivatives, and their effect on neovascularization in an experimental *in vitro* model was assessed (Bongiovi et al. 2018). These mucoadhesive micelles (diameter lower than 300 nm) were able to interact with the corneal barrier and to promote the transcorneal permeation and penetration of imatinib. Wei et al. (2025) developed zwitterionic copolymeric micelles composed of poly(2-(N-oxide-N,

N-diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate)-*block*-poly(ϵ -caprolactone), aiming to achieve transcorneal delivery of brinzolamide. The bioadhesive properties of the micelles enhanced their resistance to tear clearance and facilitated the adsorptive-mediated transcytosis. As a consequence, the micelles augmented the intraocular accumulation of the drug, which further effectively normalized the intraocular pressure in an open-angle glaucoma rat model. Thus, the micelles represent an effective platform for noninvasive therapy of glaucoma, providing the required prolonged retention and deep penetration into the cornea. An improved bioavailability of diclofenac was registered by its incorporation in methoxy-poly(ethylene glycol)-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) micelles (Li et al. 2012). *In vitro* studies showed that the micelles exhibited a 17-fold increase in penetration across the rabbit cornea compared to the simple solution of diclofenac. The pharmacokinetic profile of the micellar drug in the aqueous humor of rabbits showed a 2-fold increase in $AUC_{0-24\text{ h}}$ compared to that of the diclofenac solution. Triamcinolone acetonide was loaded in two types of micelles, namely poly(ethylene glycol)-*block*-poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PEG-*b*-PCL) and poly(ethylene glycol)-*block*-poly(lactic acid) (PEG-*b*-PLA) micelles (Safwat et al. 2020). The incorporation of the drug into PEG-*b*-PCL and PEG-*b*-PLA micelles increased its water solubility by 5- and 10-fold, respectively. Further formulation of PEG-*b*-PLA micelles in topical chitosan hydrogel provided sustained drug release and complete disappearance of the corneal inflammatory changes in a model of carrageenan-induced ocular inflammation in rabbits.

A recent study described the development of polymeric micelles (11 nm) as a platform for topical delivery of bevacizumab in pathological ocular neovascularization resulting from retinal ischemia (Yang et al. 2024). *In vitro* studies demonstrated more intensive intracellular delivery of bevacizumab in ocular cells compared to the free drug. Further, in an oxygen-induced retinopathy model, the

topical treatment with the micelles corresponded to the efficacy of the intravitreal bevacizumab injection. Thus, the study opened the opportunity to apply noninvasive administration of nanomicelles targeting posterior eye diseases instead of the invasive intravitreal injections.

Nanogels

Nanogels are three-dimensional hydrogel nanoparticles capable of improving trans/paracellular transport due to their soft and deformable structure (Fig. 1). Because of their hydrophilicity, they are biocompatible and very attractive carriers for biomedical applications. The small size and mucoadhesive properties of nanogels determine their capacity to improve ocular drug delivery (Radeva and Yoncheva 2025). Nanogels could be prepared from synthetic or natural polymers as carriers (Table 2). For example, a nanogel containing muscone was developed using Poloxamer, which belongs to the group of triblock copolymers of poly(ethylene oxide) and poly(propylene oxide). In particular, the drug was loaded in Poloxamer 407 micelles, and then a double-distilled borate buffer was added to induce the self-assembly of the nanogel (Wang et al. 2016). The nanogel demonstrated a longer retention time on the corneal surface and a higher apparent permeability coefficient (3.4-fold increase) than muscone eye drops. In addition, after instillation of the nanogel in rabbits, the maximum concentration of muscone in the aqueous humor was 6.5-fold higher compared to that after muscone drops. The authors concluded that the improved characteristics of the encapsulated drug were due to enhanced penetration of the nanogel and the prolonged residence time provided by Poloxamer.

One of the most commonly used polysaccharide carriers is chitosan, mainly due to its mucoadhesiveness, which is a prerequisite for prolongation of the retention time and better contact with ocular membranes. Thus, both processes

Table 1. Micellar formulations for ocular drug delivery.

Micellar carrier	Active molecule	Achievement	Reference
Macrogol 15 hydroxystearate	Terbinafine	More efficient penetration of the micellar drug into the corneal epithelium	Zhou et al. 2017
Poly(ethylene glycol)-distearoyl phosphatidylethanolamine	Rapamycin	Well-tolerated carrier Restoration of the ocular surface homeostasis in a model of Sjögren's syndrome	Shah et al. 2017
Poloxamer 407-D- α -tocopheryl polyethylene glycol 1000 succinate	Cyclosporine	Improved cyclosporine solubility Efficient diffusion into the sclera and sustained cyclosporine delivery	Grimaudo et al. 2018
Pluronic P123/ F127	Fexofenadine	Restored the normal conjunctival mucosa in allergic conjunctivitis	El-Shahed et al. 2024
Pluronic F127/casein	Resveratrol	Increased drug solubility Improved permeability through corneal and scleral tissues	Vivero Lopez et al. 2022
Soluplus [®]	α -lipoic acid	Enhanced drug accumulation in bovine cornea	Alvarez Rivera et al. 2016
Hyaluronic acid derivatives	Imatinib	Promotion of transcorneal permeation and penetration	Bongiovi et al. 2018
Poly(2-(N-oxide-N,N-diethylamino)ethyl methacrylate)-PCL	Brinzolamide	Normalization of intraocular pressure in a glaucoma rat model	Wei et al. 2025
mPEG- <i>b</i> -PCL	Diclofenac	Increased penetration across the cornea improved pharmacokinetics	Li et al. 2012
PEG- <i>b</i> -PCL PEG- <i>b</i> -PLA	Triamcinolone acetonide	Improved anti-inflammatory effect in a rabbit model	Safwat et al. 2020

could further enhance the ocular absorption of poorly soluble drugs. For example, since folic acid has limited ocular bioavailability, Bruno et al. (2025) encapsulated folic acid in a chitosan nanogel (312 nm). *Ex vivo* studies revealed that the encapsulated folic acid permeated through a rabbit cadaveric corneal membrane 2.6 times more slowly than the free drug. Thus, the advantage of the developed nanogel is that it provides gradual and prolonged drug release, which would further maintain therapeutic levels and reduce dosing frequency. Naringenin, a polyphenol with strong antioxidant activity, was incorporated in a chondroitin sulfate-chitosan nanogel for potential intravitreal administration in early-stage diabetic retinopathy (Zucca et al. 2025). The rationale of the study is that administration of the nanogel could reduce the number of injections and, thus, modulate side effects. *In vitro* tests in human umbilical vein endothelial cells demonstrated the capability of the nanogel to be efficiently internalized. Chitosan was also applied for the formulation of a triamcinolone acetonide-loaded nanogel aiming to improve drug delivery to the back segment of the eye and reduce its toxicity (Erdal 2025). The cytotoxicity of the free drug in endothelial cells was higher upon treatment with the free drug (74% cell viability) compared to 90% viability of cells exposed to the nanogel.

Another widely applied polysaccharide as a nanogel carrier is hyaluronic acid. Ferulic acid was encapsulated in micelles based on Pluronic F68, which were further incorporated in hyaluronan nanogel particles (300 nm) (Grimaudo et al. 2020). The micelles provided better solubility of ferulic acid as well as sustained release. The composed micelle-nanogel formulation facilitated *in vitro* wound closure in fibroblasts, suggesting the potential of the nanosystem for corneal wound healing after trauma or chemical injury. Dexamethasone was loaded in an integrin-hyaluronic- β -cyclodextrin nanogel designed as a reactive oxygen species-responsive system for topical ocular therapy of corneal neovascularization (Xiang et al. 2024). Introduction of thioketal (the ROS-responsive material) provided controlled release of the drug under conditions of oxidative stress associated with corneal neovascularization. The nanogel prolonged retention on the corneal surface for over 8 h, which was related to effective suppression of corneal

neovascularization after topical administration in a rabbit model. Zorrato et al. (2021) examined hyaluronan-cholesterol nanogels as carriers of hydrophobic drugs (dexamethasone and piroxicam) and hydrophilic drugs (tobramycin and diclofenac sodium). The bioadhesive properties of the nanogels ensured their interaction with the superficial corneal epithelium, without penetrating the stroma, thus modifying the transcorneal penetration of the loaded drugs. The results suggested that the nanogels could improve the ocular bioavailability of topically applied drugs by increasing their precorneal retention time (for hydrophobic drugs) or favoring their transcorneal permeation (for hydrophilic drugs).

Nanocrystals

Nanocrystals are nanoscale particles formulated from the active molecule itself by specific techniques such as milling, anti-solvent precipitation, and high-pressure homogenization (Fig. 1). The main advantage of this strategy is that there is no need for a carrier, as in the case of the other types of nanoparticles. This is very important taking in consideration that the carriers for ocular administration should meet specific requirements. Nanocrystal formation realizes 100% drug loading, which allows instillation of a small volume and consequently a longer retention of the applied doses. These properties make nanocrystals a very advantageous approach for ocular delivery (Geng et al. 2024). In addition, because of the nanosize of the drug crystals, the solubility is increased, which further enables drug absorption (Sharma et al. 2016). For example, triamcinolone acetonide was formulated in nanocrystal form, aiming to improve its poor water solubility. The effect of the nanocrystallization was examined in an ocular model of endotoxin-induced uveitis (Formica et al. 2023). The authors found a 40-fold higher saturation concentration of nanocrystals in simulated tear fluid compared to the pure drug. The improved dissolution and spreading of the nanocrystals were closely related to the *in vivo* results. The subconjunctival administration of the nanocrystals alleviated the inflammatory response in the anterior chamber and iris in the rabbit model. Similarly, Tuomela et al. (2014) ob-

Table 2. Examples of nanogels in ophthalmology.

Nanogel carrier	Active molecule	Achievement	Reference
Poloxamer	Muscone	Longer retention time on the corneal surface Higher apparent permeability coefficient	Wang et al. 2016
Chitosan	Folic acid	Gradual and prolonged drug release	Bruno et al. 2025
Chondroitin sulphate-chitosan	Naringenin	Efficient internalization	Zucca et al. 2025
Chitosan	Triamcinolone acetonide	Reduced toxicity	Erdal 2025
Hyaluronic acid	Ferulic acid	Potential for corneal wound healing	Grimaudo et al. 2020
Hyaluronic acid- β -cyclodextrin	Dexamethasone	Prolonged retention on the corneal surface Effective suppression of the corneal neovascularization	Xiang et al. 2024
Hyaluronan-cholesterol	Dexamethasone, piroxicam, tobramycin, diclofenac sodium	Interaction with the superficial corneal epithelium	Zorrato et al. 2021
Chitosan-alginate	Timolol maleate	2-fold higher corneal penetration than the pure drug	Ilka et al. 2018
Chitosan	Acetazolamide	Lower intraocular pressure compared to the pure drug	Abdel-Rashid et al. 2019
Nanostructured lipid carriers and	Curcumin	Higher apparent permeability coefficient and area under the curve	Liu et al. 2016

served better dissolution of brinzolamide nanocrystals and significant lowering of intraocular pressure in a rat ocular hypertensive model. The nanosize also collaborated with drug absorption. Fluorometholone nano- (201 nm) and microcrystals (9.24 μm) were developed, aiming to examine and compare their pharmacokinetics (Baba et al. 2021). After *in vivo* instillation of fluorometholone nanocrystals as eye drops, the molecule was metabolized to 20 α -dihydrofluorometholone, whose penetration was 2–6-fold higher and longer lasting compared to the microcrystals. In particular, the drug was registered in the aqueous humor 4 h after nanocrystal administration and not detected after microcrystal administration. Thus, the reduction of the size to the nanoscale level enabled penetration and dissolution rate, both closely related to pharmacokinetics.

Several studies have reported that adhesion on the ocular surface could be facilitated by nanocrystals. Acetazolamide nanocrystals (299 nm) possessed more pronounced adhesive properties than the simple powdered drug (Awde Alfonso et al. 2025). Topical administration of the nanocrystal dispersion showed a significant reduction of intraocular pressure in normotensive rabbit eyes compared to rabbits treated with acetazolamide suspension. Romero et al. (2016) developed a mixed nanocrystal formulation (approximately 250 nm) containing dexamethasone acetate and polymyxin B. The formulation was positively charged, which provided mucoadhesive properties and prolongation of ocular retention time. Gupta et al. (2010) developed a mucoadhesive *in situ* gel-forming nanosuspension containing forskolin nanocrystals. In particular, the nanosuspension underwent gelation after instillation into the cul-de-sac of the eye under the physiological pH of lacrimal fluid and temperature. The resulting hydrogel provided sustained release of the drug that could decrease the frequency of administration. In addition, the developed nanocrystal-containing hydrogel lowered intraocular pressure for 12 h, which was significantly longer than the effect of traditional eye suspension (4–6 h).

Conclusion

Conventional ophthalmic drug dosage forms have low efficiency and significant side effects. In recent years, nanotechnologies have found increasingly widespread application in ophthalmology. The development of polymeric micelles, nanogels, and nanocrystals can improve drug solubility, retention time at the site of administration, and drug absorption. These nanosystems could reduce drug toxicity (e.g., that of corticosteroids) by lowering the administered dose due to

improved pharmacokinetic properties. These improvements determine the effectiveness of nanoparticles as drug carriers and their future implementation in eye therapies.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Kiril Genov <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8253-9320>

Ventsislava Pencheva <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7486-4774>

Krassimira Yoncheva <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2704-3054>

Nevyana Veleva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8055-3451>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abdel-Rashid RS, Helal DA, Omar MM, El Sisi AM (2019) Nanogel loaded with surfactant based nanovesicles for enhanced ocular delivery of acetazolamide. *International Journal of Nanomedicine* 14: 2973–2983. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S201891>
- Alvarez-Rivera F, Fernández-Villanueva D, Concheiro A, Alvarez-Lorenzo C (2016) α -Lipoic acid in Soluplus(®) polymeric nanomicelles for ocular treatment of diabetes-associated corneal diseases. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 105(9): 2855–2863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xphs.2016.03.006>
- Awde Alfonso HG, Tartara LA, Paredes AJ, Palma SD, Formica ML (2025) Enhanced *in vivo* performance of topical ocular acetazolamide nanocrystals: A novel approach for glaucoma treatment.

- International Journal of Pharmaceutics 674: 125440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125440>
- Baba K, Hashida N, Tujikawa M, Quantock AJ, Nishida K (2021) The generation of fluorometholone nanocrystal eye drops, their metabolism to dihydrofluorometholone and penetration into rabbit eyes. International Journal of Pharmaceutics 592: 120067. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2020.120067>
- Bongiovi F, Fiorica C, Palumbo FS, Di Prima G, Giammona G, Pitarresi G (2018) Imatinib-loaded micelles of hyaluronic acid derivatives for potential treatment of neovascular ocular diseases. Molecular Pharmaceutics 15: 5031–5045. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.8b00620>
- Bruno SG, Martinez SM, Costa Gobatto C, Quinteros DA, Alaimo A, Perez OE (2025) Chitosan-TPP nanogels for ocular delivery of folic acid: Release profile, corneal permeation, and mucoadhesion assessment. Pharmaceutics 17(4): 424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics17040424>
- Diebold Y, Calonge M (2010) Applications of nanoparticles in ophthalmology. Progress in Retinal and Eye Research 29(6): 596–609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.preteyeres.2010.08.002>
- El-Shahed SA, Hassan DH, El-Nabarawi MA, El-Setouhy DA, Abdellatif MM (2024) Polymeric mixed micelle-loaded hydrogel for the ocular delivery of Fexofenadine for treating allergic conjunctivitis. Polymers 16(16): 2240. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16162240>
- Erdal E (2025) Injectable nanogels to improve triamcinolone acetonide delivery and toxicity on the treatment of eye diseases. Journal of Biomaterials Applications 39(6): 498–509. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08853282241277345>
- Formica ML, Awde Alfonso HG, Paredes AJ, Melian ME, Camacho NM, Faccio R, Tartara LI, Palma SD (2023) Development of Triamcinolone acetonide nanocrystals for ocular administration. Pharmaceutics 15(2): 683. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics15020683>
- Geng F, Fan X, Liu Y, Lu W, Wei G (2024) Recent advances in nanocrystal-based technologies applied for ocular drug delivery. Expert Opinion on Drug Delivery 21(2): 211–227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425247.2024.2311119>
- Grimaudo MA, Pescina S, Padula C, Santi P, Concheiro A, Alvarez-Lorenzo C, Nicoli S (2018) Poloxamer 407 / TPGS mixed micelles as promising carriers for cyclosporine ocular delivery. Molecular Pharmaceutics 15(2): 571–584. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.7b00939>
- Grimaudo MA, Amato G, Carbone C, Diaz-Rodriguez P, Musumeci T, Concheiro A, Alvarez-Lorenzo C, Puglisi G (2020) Micelle-nanogel platform for ferulic acid ocular delivery. International Journal of Pharmaceutics 576: 118986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2019.118986>
- Gupta S, Samanta MK, Raichur AM (2010) Dual-drug delivery system based on *in situ* gel-forming nanosuspension of forskolin to enhance antiglaucoma efficacy. AAPS PharmSciTech 11(1): 322–335. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-010-9388-x>
- Ilka R, Mohseni M, Kianirad M, Naseripour M, Ashtari K, Mehravi B (2018) Nanogel-based natural polymers as smart carriers for the controlled delivery of Timolol Maleate through the cornea for glaucoma. International Journal of Biological Macromolecules 109: 955–962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.11.090>
- Kumar A, Vimal A, Kumar A (2016) Why Chitosan? From properties to perspective of mucosal drug delivery. International Journal of Biological Macromolecules 91: 615–622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.05.054>
- Li X, Zhang Z, Li J, Sun S, Weng Y, Chen H (2012) Diclofenac/biodegradable polymer micelles for ocular applications. Nanoscale 4: 4667. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2nr30924f>
- Li S, Chen L, Fu Y (2023) Nanotechnology-based ocular drug delivery systems: recent advances and future prospects. Journal of Nanobiotechnology 21(1): 232. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-023-01992-2>
- Liu R, Sun L, Fang S, Wang S, Chen J, Xiao X, Liu C (2016) Thermo-sensitive *in situ* nanogel as ophthalmic delivery system of curcumin: development, characterization, *in vitro* permeation and *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies. Pharmaceutical Development and Technology 21(5): 576–582. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10837450.2015.1026607>
- Onugwu AL, Nwagwu CS, Onugwu OS, Echezona AC, Agbo CP, Ihim SA, Emeh P, Nnamani PO, Attama AA, Khutoryanskiy VV (2023) Nanotechnology based drug delivery systems for the treatment of anterior segment eye diseases. Journal of Controlled Release 354: 465–488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2023.01.018>
- Radeva L, Yoncheva K (2025) Nanogels – Innovative drug carriers for overcoming biological membranes. Gels 11: 124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gels11020124>
- Romero GB, Keck CM, Müller RH, Bou-Chacra NA (2016) Development of cationic nanocrystals for ocular delivery. European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics 107: 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2016.07.005>
- Safwat MA, Mansour HF, Hussein AK, Abdelwahab S, Soliman GM (2020) Polymeric micelles for the ocular delivery of triamcinolone acetonide: preparation and *in vivo* evaluation in a rabbit ocular inflammatory model. Drug Delivery 27(1): 1115–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10717544.2020.1797241>
- Shah M, Edman MC, Reddy Janga S, Yarber F, Meng Z, Klinngam W, Bushman J, Ma T, Liu S, Louie S, Mehta A, Ding C, MacKay JA, Hamm-Alvarez SF (2017) Rapamycin eye drops suppress lacrimal gland inflammation in a murine model of Sjögren's syndrome. Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science 58(1): 372–385. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.16-19159>
- Sharma OP, Patel V, Mehta T (2016) Nanocrystal for ocular drug delivery: hope or hype. Drug Delivery and Translational Research 6(4): 399–413. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13346-016-0292-0>
- Tuomela A, Liu P, Puranen J, Rönkkö S, Laaksonen T, Kalesnykas G, Oksala O, Ilkka J, Laru J, Järvinen K, Hirvonen J, Peltonen L (2014) Brinzolamide nanocrystal formulations for ophthalmic delivery: reduction of elevated intraocular pressure *in vivo*. International Journal of Pharmaceutics 467(1–2): 34–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2014.03.048>
- Vivero-Lopez M, Sparacino C, Quelle-Regaldie A, Sánchez L, Candal E, Barreiro-Iglesias A, Huete-Toral F, Carracedo G, Otero A, Concheiro A, Alvarez-Lorenzo C (2022) Pluronic®/casein micelles for ophthalmic delivery of resveratrol: *In vitro*, *ex vivo*, and *in vivo* tests. International Journal of Pharmaceutics 628: 122281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2022.122281>
- Wang G, Nie Q, Zang C, Zhang B, Zhu Q, Luo G, Wang S (2016) Self-assembled thermoresponsive nanogels prepared by reverse micelle → Positive micelle method for ophthalmic delivery of Muscone, a poorly water-soluble drug. Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences 105(9): 2752–2759. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xphs.2016.02.014>
- Wei Q, Zhu C, Yuan G, Jin J, Zhang J, Fan W, Piao Y, Shao S, Lin S, Xiang J, Shen Y (2025) Active trans-corneal drug delivery with ocular adhesive micelles for efficient glaucoma therapy. Journal of Controlled Release 377: 578–590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2024.11.050>

- Xiang Y, Qiu Z, Ding Y, Du M, Gao N, Cao H, Zuo H, Cheng H, Gao X, Zheng S, Wan W, Huang X, Hu K (2024) Dexamethasone-loaded ROS stimuli-responsive nanogels for topical ocular therapy of corneal neovascularization. *Journal of Controlled Release* 372: 874–884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2024.07.012>
- Yang R, Tang S, Xie X, Jin C, Tong Y, Huang W, Zan X (2024) Enhanced ocular delivery of beva via ultra-small polymeric micelles for non-invasive anti-VEGF therapy. *Advanced Materials* 36(32): e2314126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202314126>
- Yoncheva K (2020) Benefits and perspectives of nanoparticles based on chitosan and sodium alginate. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences* 73(3): 291–305. <https://doi.org/10.7546/CRABS.2020.03.01>
- Yoncheva K, Calleja P, Agueros M, Petrov P, Miladinova I, Tsvetanov Ch, Irache JM (2012) Stabilized micelles as delivery vehicles for paclitaxel. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 436: 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2012.06.030>
- Zhou HY, Hao JL, Wang S, Zheng Y, Zhang WS (2013) Nanoparticles in the ocular drug delivery. *International Journal of Ophthalmology* 6(3): 390–396. <https://doi.org/10.3980/j.issn.2222-3959.2013.03.25>
- Zhou T, Zhu L, Xia H, He J, Liu S, He S, Wang L, Zhang J (2017) Micelle carriers based on macrogol 15 hydroxystearate for ocular delivery of terbinafine hydrochloride: *In vitro* characterization and *in vivo* permeation. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 109: 288–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2017.08.020>
- Zoratto N, Forcina L, Matassa R, Mosca L, Familiari G, Musarò A, Mattei M, Coviello T, Di Meo C, Matricardi P (2021) Hyaluronan-cholesterol nanogels for the enhancement of the ocular delivery of therapeutics. *Pharmaceutics* 13(11): 1781. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics13111781>
- Zucca G, Viganì B, Valentino C, Ruggeri M, Marchesi N, Pascale A, Giovilli G, Malavasi L, Sandri G, Rossi S (2025) Chondroitin sulphate-chitosan based nanogels loaded with Naringenin- β -Cyclodextrin complex as potential tool for the treatment of diabetic retinopathy: A formulation study. *International Journal of Nanomedicine* 20: 907–932. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S488507>